

USAGE AND ANALYSIS OF SUGARCANE BAGASSE AND EPOXY RESIN COMPOSITE MATERIAL FOR GYROSCOPIC SELF-BALANCING E-VEHICLE

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Abstract: This project aims to explore the potential of utilizing sugarcane bagasse, an agricultural waste product, combined with epoxy resin to fabricate composite materials suitable for the construction of components in gyrosopic self-balancing electric vehicles (E-vehicles). The study involves the analysis of mechanical properties, such as tensile strength, flexural strength, and impact resistance, of the composite materials. Additionally, considerations regarding the environmental impact and cost-effectiveness of using sugarcane bagasse as a reinforcement material will be addressed. The findings of this research will provide valuable insights into the feasibility of employing sustainable composite materials in the automotive industry, particularly for innovative E-vehicle designs.

Keywords—Sugarcane bagasse powder, epoxy resin-HY951, Hardner-LY551.

1. INTRODUCTION

Modern materials often reach the end of their useful life in the never-ending search for reduced weight, maximum strength, and reduced cost in order to maximise performance. As a result, engineers, chemists, and material scientists are always working to create entirely new materials or better existing ones. One example of the latter kind is composites. The last 40 to 50 years have seen an enormous increase in the manufacturing of synthetic composites, with those that combine tiny fibres with different resins (polymers) controlling the market. Considering the growing threats to the environment and the global energy crises, Scientists throughout the world are turning their focus to potential solutions to synthetic fibres. Since the 1990s, natural fibre composites have emerged as a viable alternative to glass-reinforced composites in numerous applications. Natural fibre in

composites is said to provide environmentally friendly advantages such as increased dependency on non-renewable energy sources, low pollutant emissions, low greenhouse gas emissions, improved energy recovery, and component end-of-life biodegradability. Such higher environmental performance is a key motivation for greater future usage of natural fibre composites.

2. CHARACTERISTICS OF THE COMPOSITES

One or more discontinuous phases are inserted in a continuous phase to form a composite material. The discontinuous phase is harder and stronger than the continuous phase and is known as the reinforcement or reinforcing material, whereas the continuous phase is referred to

as the matrix. Composites' qualities are greatly influenced by the properties of its component materials, as well as their distribution and interaction. The composite qualities may be the volume fraction of some of the constituents' attributes, or the constituents may combine synergistically to produce enhanced or superior properties. In addition to the nature of the component materials, the geometry of the reinforcement form and size distribution has a significant impact on the composite's qualities. The characteristics are also affected by the reinforcement's concentration distribution and direction. The shape of the discontinuous phase, which can be spherical, cylindrical, or rectangular cross sanctioned prisms or platelets, as well as the size and size distribution, which control the texture of the material and volume fraction, determine the interfacial area, which is important in determining the extent of the interaction between the reinforcement and the matrix.

3. CLASSIFICATION

Classification based on the geometry of a typical unit of reinforcement is useful since the geometry of the reinforcement is responsible for the mechanical characteristics and high performance of composites. Composites are often classified into two major types. 1. Particulate Composites 2. Fibrous Composites

4. COMPONENTS OF A COMPOSITE MATERIAL

In its most basic form, a composite material is one that is made up of at least two components that interact together to provide material qualities that differ from those of the individual constituents. In reality, most composites are made up of a bulk material known as the 'matrix' and some form of reinforcement, which is added largely to boost the matrix's strength and stiffness.

4.1 Role of Matrix in a Composite

When the same materials are in a fibrous state, they display extremely strong strength qualities; however, to acquire these capabilities, the fibres must be connected with an appropriate matrix. The matrix separates the fibres from one another to prevent abrasion and the production of new surface defects, and it serves as a bridge to hold the fibres in place. A good matrix should be able to flex easily under applied load, transmit the load to the fibres, and have an equally distributed stress concentration.

4.2 Used Materials as Matrix in Composites

In its most basic form, a composite material is one that is made up of at least two components that interact together to provide material qualities that differ from those of the individual constituents. In practice, most composites are made up of a bulk material known as the matrix and some type of reinforcement applied to boost the matrix's strength and stiffness.

5. BULK PHASES

5.1 Metal Matrices

Metal matrix composites have several desirable features as compared to organic matrices. These include strength retention at greater temperatures, increased transverse strength, improved electrical conductivity, superior thermal conductivity, and increased erosion resistance, among other things. However, the main drawback of metal matrix composites is that they have greater densities and hence worse specific mechanical characteristics than polymer matrix composites. Another significant challenge is the high energy demand for fabricating such composites.

5.2 Polymer Matrices

A wide range of polymeric materials, both thermosetting and thermoplastic, are employed as matrix materials in composites. Resin matrices have significant benefits and limits.

5.3 Ceramic Matrices

Carbide is useful in high-temperature applications and when environmental assault is a concern. Because ceramics have weak tension and shear characteristics, the majority of reinforcing applications are in the form of particulate materials such as zinc and calcium phosphate. Ceramic Matrix Composites (CMCs) are materials that employ a ceramic matrix and are reinforced with small fibres or whiskers consisting of silicon carbide or boron nitride.

6. TYPES OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

Composite materials are roughly categorised into the following categories:

6.1 Fiber-Reinforced Composites

Reinforced composites are commonly used in industrial applications because to their high specific strength and stiffness. Composites' superior structural performance makes them promising for use in biological applications. In this sort of composite, the second phase consists of fibres scattered throughout the matrix, which might be plastic or metal. The

Fig.1 (a)

Fig. 1 (b)

Fig.1 (c)

Fig.1 (d)

Fig.1 (a) Random fiber (short fiber) reinforced

Fig.1 (b) Particles as the reinforcement Composites

Fig.1 (c) Continuous fiber (long fiber) reinforced

Fig.(d) Flat flakes as the reinforcement Composites

volume portion ranges from a few percent to as much as 70%. The usage of fibre reinforcement is done to achieve high strength and modulus. As a result, the fibres must have a greater modulus than the matrix material in order to transfer the load from the matrix more efficiently.

6.2 Dispersion Hardened Material

This material has tiny particles ranging in size from $0.01\mu\text{m}$ to $0.14\mu\text{m}$ scattered throughout the matrix. The concentration ranges from 1% to 15% by volume. These small particles restrict dislocation movement in the material, resulting in extremely high strength. Furthermore, these materials have improved high temperature strength and creep resistance.

6.3 Particulate Composite

Composites with particles ranging from $1\mu\text{m}$ to $200\mu\text{m}$ are disseminated in the matrix, with a volume fraction of $0.01 V_f$ to $0.85 V_f$.

6.4 Natural Fiber Composites

Nowadays, research and engineering focus is changing from typical synthetic fibre composite to lingo-cellulosic natural fibre composite because to benefits like as high strength-to-weight ratio, non-carcinogenicity, and biodegradability. The word "natural fibre" refers to a broad spectrum of vegetable, animal, and mineral fibres. However, in the composite sector, it mainly refers to wood fibre and agro-based fibres such as blast, leaf, seed, and stem.

Fig.2: Current technological process for extraction of suga juice from cane in a sugarcane mill

Fig.3: Bagasses

This is also referred to as a fibrous residue (Figure 3), which remains after the juice is extracted from the sugar cane stalk. It is composed of water, fibres, and trace quantities of soluble substances. Each component's percentage contribution varies according on the type, ripeness, harvesting technique, and crushing plant performance.

Table-1 : Average Bagasse Compositions

ITEM	PERCENTAGE
Cellulose	46
Hemicelluloses	24.5
Lignin	19.95
Fats and waxes	3.5
Ash	2.4
Silica	2
Other elements	1.7

Bagasse is primarily used as a burning raw material in sugarcane mill furnaces. This technique is inefficient due to bagasse's poor caloric power. The sugar cane mill management also faces issues with the environmental protection agency's "clean air" laws owing to the quality of smoke spewed into the atmosphere. Burning accounts for around 85% of bagasse output.

Despite this, there is an abundance of bagasse. Usually, this surplus is deposited on unoccupied fields, changing the landscape. Bagasse accounts for approximately 9% of total ethanol production. Ethanol is not only an effective substitute for fossil fuels, but it is also an ecologically benign fuel. Aside from that, ethanol is a very flexible chemical raw material from which a wide range of chemicals may be manufactured; nevertheless, because to the low level of sucrose remaining in bagasse, ethanol production efficiency is rather poor. With an increased emphasis on fuel efficiency, natural fibres such as bagasse-based composites are finding new applications in autos, railway coaches and buses for public transportation. There is a great chance to manufacture bagasse-based composites for a variety of uses in building and construction, such as boards and blocks, reconstituted wood and flooring tiles. Different volume fractions by weight of bagasse fibre were combined with matrix material, and specimens were created. The current project aims to create a new class of natural fibre epoxy on sugarcane bagasse waste composite materials. Tensile, flexural, and impact characteristics were investigated (with different amounts of sugarcane bagasse waste). The storage modulus, loss modulus, and damping properties of various sugarcane bagasse waste with epoxy composites were investigated using dynamic mechanical analysis. Dynamic mechanical study was conducted on sugarcane bagasse waste and epoxy composites.

7.MATERIALS AND METHODS

7.1 Composite Preparations

To prepare the composite, following materials are required.

1. Sugarcane Bagasse fibers
2. Epoxy resin
3. Hardner

7.2 Preparation of Sugarcane Bagasse Fiber

This sugarcane stalk consists of an outer rind and an interior pith. Bagasse's outer layers are made of a hard fibrous substance known as rind, while the interior is made of a soft material known as pith. The pith contains short fibres and the majority of the sucrose, whereas the rind has longer and finer fibre. After around two weeks, the long bagasse fibres (rind section alone) were trimmed to a length of 10mm to 40mm (optimal fibre length determined by a single fibre pull out test) and width of 1mm to 4mm using a pair of scissors. Fungi did not grow during storage because the bagasse samples had a low moisture level. The bagasse samples were then washed with pressurised water for approximately one hour. This technique extracts fine bagasse particles, sugar residues, and organic compounds from the samples. Next, the fibres were dried using a hair dryer.

7.3 Epoxy Resin and Hardner

Epoxy resins are relatively low-molecular-weight prepolymers that may be processed under a range of circumstances. These over unsaturated polyester resins have two significant advantages: they may be partially cured and kept in that form, and they shrink very little during cure.

7.4 Preparation of Composite Laminates

Two hardwood moulds measuring 150x150x3.5 mm and 130x80x3 mm were used to cast the composite sheet. The first mould size is used to create samples for tensile strength testing, while the second mould size is utilised for flexural testing. The first batch of samples had fibre volume fractions of 5, 10, 20, 25, and 30%. The samples were prepared using the usual hand lay-up procedure. For each volume fraction of fibres, a determined amount of epoxy

resin and hardener ratio of 10:1 by weight was completely mixed in a glass jar and placed in a vacuum chamber to eliminate any air bubbles that were introduced. Initially, this treatment lasted 10 minutes. The mixture was re-stirred, and the vacuum technique was repeated for another 10 minutes to remove the remaining bubbles. For rapid and simple removal of composite sheets, a mould release sheet was placed over the glass plate, and a mould release spray was sprayed to the mold's inner surface. After placing the mould on a glass sheet, a thin layer of the mixture (1mm mm 39 thickness) was poured. The needed number of fibres were then dispersed throughout the mixture. The remaining material was then poured into the mould. The development of air bubbles was carefully avoided. Pressure was then applied from the top, and the mould was left to cure at room temperature for 72 hours. During the application of pressure, part of the epoxy and hardener mixture is squeezed out. This loss has been carefully considered throughout the manufacture of composite sheets. After 72 hours, the samples were removed from the mould. A shot shows the composite and some of the specimens sliced for further research. After cutting, they were stored in an airtight container. The samples for the tensile, flexural, and hardness tests are produced in the following volume fractions.

Table-2: Volume fractions of different samples

S. No.	Composites	Composition
1	EBSF-1	Epoxy + sugarcane bagasse fiber (0% Volume Fraction)
2	EBSF-2	Epoxy + sugarcane bagasse fiber (5% Volume Fraction)
3	EBSF-3	Epoxy + sugarcane bagasse fiber (10% Volume Fraction)
4	EBSF-4	Epoxy + sugarcane bagasse fiber (20% Volume Fraction)
5	EBSF-5	Epoxy + sugarcane bagasse fiber (25% Volume Fraction)
6	EBSF-6	Epoxy + sugarcane bagasse fiber (30% Volume Fraction)

Fig.4 : Mold Preparation for preparing the samples

Fig.5(a) Tensile Test Specimen

Fig.5(b) Flexural Test Specimen

Fig.5: Samples prepared for tensile test and flexural testing

8.CHARACTERIZATION OF MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

Tensile and flexural tests were performed on the INSTRON 3382,100 KN Universal Testing Machine at a temperature of $23\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and relative humidity of $50\pm 5\%$. Tensile testing were conducted according to ASTM D638 and flexural tests

according to ASTM D790. Table 3 shows a summary of all tests performed.

Table-3: Summary of Tests

Testing	Machine Used	Working Variables	No of Specimen	Standard Used
Tensile	INSTRON 3382 UTM	Load cell : 100 KN Rate : 5 mm/min	6 x 5 = 30	ASTM D638
Flexural	INSTRON 3382 UTM	Load cell : 100 KN Rate : 1.32 mm/min	6 x 5 = 30	ASTM D790

8.1 Tensile Testing

Tensile testing determines a material's capacity to withstand forces that tend to tear it apart, as well as the amount to which the material stretches before fracture. For tensile testing, the specimens were cut to the dimensions given in Figure 6 and Table 4. The tests were conducted in a typical laboratory setting of $23^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $50 \pm 5\%$ relative humidity. The Universal Testing Machine UTM, INSTRON 3382, was operated at a cross-head speed of 5 mm/minute. The Universal Testing Machine (UTM, INSTRON 3382) is used for tensile testing. The specimens were placed vertically in the grips of the testing machine. The grips were then adjusted evenly and firmly to minimise slipping, with the gauge length set at 50mm. The average five test results were selected for each fibre mix of sugarcane bagasse fiber-based composites.

Fig.6: Dimensions of Tensile Test Specimen

Table-4: Dimensions of Tensile Test Specimen

Dimension	Value, mm
Thickness, T	3.5
Width W	25
Length, L	120
Gauge length, G	50

As the tensile test begins, the specimen elongates and its resistance increases, which is recorded by a load cell. The load value (F) is recorded until the specimen ruptures. The tensile characteristics for yield strength and elongation at break will be calculated using the instrument software that comes with the device. The following are the basic relationships used to derive these properties: Tensile strength at yield = maximum load measured / cross-sectional area.

8.2 Flexural Testing

Flexural strength refers to the material's capacity to withstand bending forces applied perpendicular to its longitudinal axis. It is sometimes referred to as cross-breaking strength, which is the highest stress produced when a bar-shaped test piece, functioning as a simple beam, is exposed to a perpendicular bending force. The stress reduced by the flexural load is a mixture of compressive and tensile stresses. There are two ways for determining the flexural characteristics of materials: the three-point loading system and the four-point loading system. ASTM D790 describes a three-point loading technique applied to a supported beam. Flexural test 43 is vital for both designers and manufacturers in the shape of a beam. If the service failure is considerable in bending, the flexural test is more appropriate for design and specification than the tensile test. Test pieces measuring 126 mm × 12.57 mm × 3mm were manufactured in accordance with ASTM D790 standards. The test components were tested flat on a support span, yielding a span-to-depth ratio of 16.

This signifies that the span is sixteen times the thickness of the specimen. According to ASTM D790, the width and depth of the specimen were measured to the closest 0.03mm at the centre of the support span. The test components were then positioned on two supports, and load was applied. The spacing between two support spans (L) was specified at 49.6 mm. Figure 7 depicts the placement of the loading nose and support attachment.

Fig.7 : Loading Nose and Support arrangement

Flexural testing were performed on a Universal Testing Machine (UTM, INSTRON 3382) under conventional laboratory conditions of 23°C ± 2°C and 50 ± 5% relative humidity. The load was applied at the prescribed cross-head rate of 1.32 mm per minute. The constant load was then applied to the test component, and deflection was recorded. The testing will be halted when the highest strain in the specimen's outer surface reaches 5% or when rupture occurs. Three consistent test piece results were selected for each fibre loading mix. When a homogeneous elastic material is evaluated using a three-point system, the highest stress occurs at the middle. The maximum stress is connected to the load and sample dimensions, and it is computed using the equation of $\sigma = \frac{3PL}{2bd^2}$, where σ = maximum stress, MPa P = applied load, N L = support span, mm b = specimen width tested, mm d = specimen depth tested, mm.

8.3 Macro-Hardness

The Rockwell Hardness tester is used to assess macro-hardness. A 1/4-inch diamond indenter is pressed into the material with a load F. The operating capacity of the

hardness machine is 150 kg. The machine has an accuracy of 0.1 gramme. In this investigation, the force is $F = 60 \text{ Kg}$, and Rockwell hardness is computed by reading the red indicator.

9. RESULTS

9.1 Mechanical Characteristics of composites

The experimental results of composite testing by varying content are presented in table 5.

Table-5: Mechanical properties with varying %

S. No	Fiber Content (%)	Orientation (deg)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Flexural Strength (MPa)	Hardness (HRL)
1	-	Random	18.61	19.03	46
2	5	Random	27.03	24.20	58
3	10	Random	46.87	32.97	72
4	20	Random	58.36	59.60	93
5	25	Random	52.68	53.36	97
6	30	Random	46.07	51.42	98

Fig.8: Variation of tensile strength with different of sugarcane bagasse fiber

9.2 Effect of fiber content on tensile properties

The accompanying chart clearly shows that tensile strength improves with increasing volume percentage of sugarcane bagasse fibre. It reaches its peak at 20% volume percent and gradually drops as volume fraction increases.1

9.3 Flexural Strength

Figure 3.2 depicts the fluctuation in flexural strength with different volume fractions of sugarcane bagasse fibre.

9.4 Effect of fiber content on flexural strength

The accompanying chart clearly shows that flexural strength rises with increasing volume percentage of sugarcane bagasse fibre. It reaches its peak at 20% volume percent and gradually drops as volume fraction increases.

Fig.9: Variation of flexural strength with different fiber loading conditions

Fig.10: Variation of Rockwell macro hardness with values different volume fraction of fiber composites

9.5 Effect of Fiber Loading on Macro Hardness

The accompanying chart clearly shows that hardness rises with increasing volume percentage of sugarcane bagasse fibre. It reaches its peak at a volume percentage of 20% and thereafter stays nearly constant.

10. CONCLUSIONS

The study's findings suggest that a usable composite with good qualities may be effectively developed by employing sugarcane bagasse fibre as a reinforcing agent in the polymer matrix. This leads to various findings about the mechanical characteristics of composites, including tensile strength, flexural and macro

hardness, as well as the influence of fibre content. Tensile strength gradually climbed to 20 percent as the fibre content in unsaturated polymers grew in volume %. Tensile strength decreased as the fibre content in composite rose. This phenomena has been exacerbated by increased fiber-to-fiber contact and matrix dispersion. Flexural strength and hardness increase by up to 20% before dropping. Finally, sugarcane bagasse fibre improves the tensile, flexural, and impact characteristics of unsaturated polymers. The study found that the optimal for select performance in tensile, flexural, and macro hardness testing was 20% fibre content.

11.FUTURE WORKS

The findings of this study indicated several new possibilities for further investigation. They are:

- 1.Determination of chemical elements inside the abundant sugarcane bagasse fibre in terms of chemical composition and impacts on certain qualities.
- 2.The research expanded to include creep, fatigue, compressive, shear strength, chemical resistance, and electrical qualities.
- 3.The application of various chemical promoters and coupling agents can be investigated.
- 4.Other epoxy-hardener polymeric matrix systems can be investigated.
- 5.A hybrid composite made up of different fibres, such as glass fibre and sugarcane bagasse fibre, can be examined since it will undoubtedly improve the performance of the composite.
- 6.Optimizing the aforementioned data can improve the precision of the findings.
7. Fibres can be chemically treated. It can enhance the mechanical characteristics of the composite.
- 8.varied composites may be made with varied fibre lengths. Length can help improve the mechanical characteristics of composites.
- 9.Placing the fibres at different angles allows for the creation of various composites. This can have an impact on the

mechanical characteristics of composite materials.

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